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IMPROVING THE LINK BETWEEN HIGHER EDUCATION AND EMPLOYMENT IN INDIA

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ABSTRACT

In this document we discuss the system of higher education in India together with the link between education and employment. At present, there is a great need in India to change the structure of the higher education system and a need for expansion of the education scale together with vocational orientation of education to create a more robust system consistent with market needs. Based on this hypothesis, we analyze the relationships between each of them the two aspects of education and employment respectively. In this document, the factors and the transfer mechanism of the influence that education has on employment is also Explained. Then the theoretical models of the relationship between education and employment is built up. Finally, we use the secondary data to evaluate the status quo for Unemployment in India. Our research strongly indicates that the development of Vocational training is necessary in India. Adjust the structure on education and training facilities to the realities of the labour market will be advantageous for Employment degrees. In addition, governing bodies need not depend solely on the creation of jobs as a solution to the employment crisis, but should promote the development of entrepreneurship among India's young people. Entrepreneurship is indispensable for catering to the need for employment for such a large population. Vocational orientation and professionalization higher education has unintended effects on employment.

Purpose – The purpose of this paper is to emphasize the creation of job-oriented policies affecting the Indian education system.

Design/methodology/approach – The focus lies on group discussions.

Findings – analytical, qualitative data

Research limitations/implications – Our findings are primarily based on secondary data.

Practical implications – The findings provide guidelines for educational policies, and hence useful for upgrading the higher education system in India.

Originality/value – We take a solution-oriented approach through critical analysis.

Paper type: Research paper.

INTRODUCTION

Higher education and employment are undoubtedly closely linked. Changes in the education sector directly affects employment in politics, finance and structure. On currently, unemployment in India is increasing day by day. One of the different roots the high unemployment rate lies in the system of higher education and the lack of encouragement of entrepreneurship. We define higher education as university education 216 in different streams. In the context of our paper, we believe that higher education is not professional based. Although there is a trend towards professional courses in India, the concept has not yet grown in popularity. Effective training for employment, the connection between employers' demands and the results of our current education system, the implications of a rapidly globalizing world and what must happen in order to achieve appropriate goals Education in the 21st century is the subject of concern. India is the third largest higher education system in the world after China and China United States of America. India's higher education landscape consists of government, government and private institutions. There are 20 central universities that are run by Central Government. At central universities, education is supposed to be cheaper. In all cases, In particular, technical main characters become expensive even at government institutions.

In addition, there are 42 specialized colleges, including technical institutes or management, which is also run by the central government. India has 215 state boards' universities, funded and coordinated by the federal governments. Other universities, such as 100 "Deemed Universities" received their university status from University Grants Commission and initiated by private economic initiatives, but funded by government funds. Private universities and institutions of distant learning are growing number and popularity, as state institutions are increasingly meeting the increased demand for higher education since the 1990s. The higher education offered by private institutions in higher education is motivated by profit rather than in accordance with India's employment to market. The majority of the working population in India is employed in the agricultural sector. Recent research from the National Sample Survey Organization shows that the creation of jobs in India over the past year was limited, especially in the agricultural sector, and there was a major withdrawal from the workforce, especially by women¹. It's a shift in popularity for higher education among young people, but labour force participation has declined. The importance of the informal sector is growing, but the trends in

education are not responding to this development. Main issues that arise when discussing education in connection with employment are differences between rural and urban trends, gender differences, illiteracy, the effects of federalism and the consequences of traditional ones social structures such as the caste system.

EDUCATION

Although education is a very important condition for employment, India has to face many education-related problems. The huge shortage of teachers is a national issue. According to a study by the National University of Educational Planning & Administration (UNEPA), India is short of 1.2 million teachers². The number of children between 6 and 14 years who do not attend school, lies at a shocking 42 million. The study indicates that 16% of all villages do not have primary schools and 17% of schools employ only one teacher.

In addition, students who drop out of school present a serious problem for Indians. Education system As an analysis of data from the District Information System for Education in India Sample, Grade, which is the highest grade in the elementary school cycle, has a dropout rate of 15.9%, while attrition rates in grades 6 and 7 are 10% lower. The higher the school grade, The least likely students are to quit smoking. One of the main reasons for these dropouts is economic. 60% of children who responded to the survey declared the need to supplement income. Through housework and domestic work . Another 30% of children declared that they work to financially help their families. The study found that the cost of school supplies is another important cause of abandonment. Among children who dropped out of school, 9-10% did Due to poor academic performance, 5 to 8% felt that they could not catch up on school work they had been lost due to the absence, and 14% dropped out of school due to the discouraging influence of their teachers ⁸. Regarding the seriousness of the problems at the levels of primary education, the approach of the government budget for primary and secondary education as opposed to higher education It seems logical.

Despite the serious problems at the level of primary education, higher education system in India has grown steadily over the past century, and has experienced exponential growth since the 1990s. The higher education system in India is now one of the largest in the world the government has played an important role in financing and support. However, higher education does not always meet the structural needs of the Indian market. Statistics published by the University Grants Commission state that 36% of the research students in the higher education system of India are enrolled in the arts, followed by science (18%) and engineering and technology (16%). Enrolment in medicine is respectively under 4%. Only 2% of Indian students are enrolled in law programs, and a also under 3% are enrolled in education. This indicates that social needs, such as health, Education and jurisdiction

are not reflected in the contribution of students in higher education. Education system. Rashtriya Uchattar Shiksha Abhiyan (RUSA) is a central government sponsored program that targets state higher education. It allows the sovereignty of the state. RUSA uses particular strategies to address problems of expansion, excellence and equity. However, public higher education in India faces serious problems. Former first the minister, Manmohan Singh, evaluated the higher education system in 2007 as follows: "Our university system is, in many places, in poor condition. In almost half of the districts in the country, enrolments in higher education are abysmally low; almost two thirds of our universities and 90% of our schools have a lower than average grade in quality parameters I am concerned that university appointments have become politicized and they have been subject to caste and communal considerations."

Higher education is not only driven by favouritism in the appointment of agents, but also for market opportunities and entrepreneurial zeal. Many institutions are taking advantage. The relaxed regulatory environment to offer 'grades' not approved by the authorities. Public Higher education is reluctant to respond to the demands of the labor market. Many "non-profit" Organizations develop financial methods to divert profits. This further fuels the growth of private higher education. India's private education sector was estimated at \$ 40 billion in 2008 increased to \$ 68 billion in 2012.¹¹ observing the educational infrastructure through statistics, approximately 40% of the Indian population is illiterate, while the ability to the system of higher education, private and public, can only house 7% of India in university age population. This educational environment does not promote widespread education. The growth of higher education institutions, illustrated in appendix 1, shows a growth almost totally caused by the increase in private institutions of postsecondary education.

In the last ten years, the number of universities and colleges has experienced exponential growth. However, student enrolment rates have grown at a slower pace. The RUSA government program and the process of privatization of higher education in India is responsible for this development. On the one hand, RUSA is providing strategic financing for higher and technical public institutions, to boost regulatory higher education State-wide policies. On the other hand, the percentile increase in private schools, expensive For students, it makes good quality higher education unavailable to less wealthy students. As a consequence of the cost of higher education, the enrolment of women is significantly lower than that of men. The table in Appendix 2 indicates that in the 2010-2011 academic year, there were 10 million fewer women enrolled than men, while the gender enrolment gap was 2 million in 1990-1991.

The initiative of the Indian government "Education for all" began after the Millennium and made in April 2009, when a clause was added to the Indian constitution, giving each child between the ages of 6 and 14 the right to education. In the present, Government and state efforts in the education sector focus on problems in primary and secondary level, and not at the level of higher education. The government allocated only 4% of the gross domestic product of education in 2012, which included all primary education, secondary and higher education 15. Changes in the higher education sector are therefore Very left for private initiatives.

EMPLOYMENT

“Employment is so crucial for development. Employment creates a sense of self dependence and independence that is very fundamental for development not only in individual but socially and nationally. The value of education in employment and Employment for a healthy, productive and peaceful society cannot be underestimated.”

Work means financial freedom for women. Providing access to education, Health services for children; presents an alternative to violence for idle young people Employment is essential for successful sustainable development. surely, With an advanced society, individuals can lead healthy and productive lives, Access and participation in resources necessary for an appropriate standard of living Community life and work make development happen. Job creation and full For decades, employment has been part of the development agenda and sometimes Top of list, and may lose priority to GDP growth or other economies Priority. "

In 2013, work issues have returned to the spotlight of development and there are good reasons. According to International Labour Organization, there are over 200 million people 17 unemployed around the world. In recent years we have witnessed the global financial crisis. The country was untouched and caused a massive recession and a large loss of employment. Five Years later, the world is still short of about 67 million jobs. In addition to catching up before the crisis Employment level, total number of jobs required to maintain current employment rate it continues to grow every year. Population projections suggest that the world needs upwards Of the 500 million new jobs until 2020, the majority of developing countries are relatively A young population has entered the labour force¹⁸. Promoting population growth and job creation is improving the quality of education. Education contributing to overall economic growth by improving labour efficiency, As a result, personal productivity is improved. Qualified workers Education can provide individuals with the necessary market skills Related to the economy.

However, this only happens if the quality of education is guaranteed. The problem is most education systems have creative thinking, communication skills, and Problem solving and other soft skills essential to the job market. And again not focus on entrepreneurship development. To change and maximize this situation Educational benefits and collaboration are required while improving the employment aptitude of graduates between government, private sector and educational institutions. Such collaboration Help prepare workers by adjusting the supply and demand of skilled workers Graduates while ensuring that the system operates in a favourable policy environment. For example, the German apprentice dual system is often advertised as another model. A country that reduces youth unemployment. This program is important for young people Work experience to make them more employable and promote employment transition. The German system has a government Private sector where the cost and development of training content are shared jointly by both body. Apprentices also provide a professional network for young people before admission Equipped them with workforce, expert connections, hard skills, and motivation Acquire soft skills. Learning from the success of the apprentice program offers Guidance on how you can reduce youth unemployment.

The relationship between education policy and employment sector requirements Established based on national politics. However, the main concern in India Current politics includes financial relations, national security, and Central state relations. India has a long tradition of federalism and a strong regional identity. Since the 1990s, these powerful federal traditions have increasingly presented problems Political scene where the state government competes with the central government Privilege to make decisions in various fields. In constant conflict and confusion State-centre relations, education and employment are not the main issues

The current governing body. Both education and employment were categorized "Social, economic, and human development" by the Central State Relations Committee Therefore, it is third in the list of areas that need reform¹⁹. Political struggle between thus, federalism and centralization pose challenges to the universal reform that is desperately needed Both in education and employment.

Unemployment is a national issue, but data is available from several federal states We face a significantly higher unemployment rate than others. And cause of Signs of unemployment varies from state to state. There is no general cure this high unemployment rate. Still, education initiatives need to consider each an individual state and its specific situation.

India's employment sector has witnessed massive development and is increasing The last 30 years. Lack of institutional response to retraining requirements and Changes in the labor market further

widen the gap between rich and poor. Structural changes shift most of the workforce from the agricultural sector to the industrial sector And service department. The majority of the working population still occupies the agricultural sector. However, the productivity of workers in the industrial sector is Agriculture. Urbanization and the inevitable transfer of the workforce have played a major role It played a role in government policy choices and ignited the demand for workforce retraining. Now work in the agriculture sector is more effective, Mobilize your workforce through education and vocational training to meet the following needs: India and its market in the 21st century.

As suggested by the work participation statistics shown in Appendix , the work Participation rate and employment growth are almost equal in rural and urban areas Trend. But statistics point out the lack of employment of Indian women. Indian The labor market currently does not fully demonstrate its potential. More than 60% of India Women are not actively involved in payroll work²⁰. Factoring the generation of women India's GDP will have great economic consequences. Higher education and Quality vocational training, especially accessible to women, will be of great help. However, the cultural structure and traditional role of women in Indian society, Especially in lower castes, it creates a barrier to this scheme. Education accessibility An essential starting point, but may not be the final answer to the lack of engagement issue Female.

Social separation with ancient roots in the caste system, and religion The vast subcontinental tribal diversity establishes restrictions on social and work mobility In India. The Indian Constitution offers specific articles to people in "scheduled caste" (SC) and "scheduled tribe" (ST). These articles are aimed at reducing discrimination Against these listed castes and tribes, and Guarantee of SC and ST seats to increase political participation Access to education for SC and ST members²¹. The government policy Caste members who have been at a disadvantage throughout history, and their improvements Education and equal opportunities in the job market. The reality of the job market is It is different from what the law suggests. For example, when comparing the status of a paid job Stats of prime age men, in order caste muslims and in order caste hindus, Borooah et al. Shows that Muslims have an "employment deficit" ²². Government policy Job reservations diversified representatives within the Indian work group. Nevertheless, Lower caste people and certain religious and tribal groups are still at a disadvantage. Differentiating opportunities in the job market is not just rooted in education, Increased opportunities for higher education can be attributed to tribes, religion, The difference in caste employment.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the unemployment problem and the growing social division are It is solved through drastic structural changes in the higher education system. In particular The distribution of registrations by field needs to be restructured. For example, in India, Despite the lack of qualified teachers, only 3% of college students enroll in education. Therefore, especially public universities adapt to market demands, Therefore, it will be more attractive to students. As a result, non-rich students Has access to higher education that allows stable entry into the job market. Currently, higher education and quality vocational training are not available Most of India's potential workforce. Since providing education to the disadvantaged

Individuals in society become difficult because of traditional structures and customs. Promoting entrepreneurship is a way to make a difference. To be involved efficiently Indian women and lower caste or discriminated tribes and religious people Economic, self-employed and skill training efforts are required. Overall, struggle The struggle between the private and public actors, and between the central and state actors is creating Barrier to improvement. Leave most of the work to non-governmental grassroots Organization and society.